

Transitional Probabilistic Approach for Detection and Rejection of Vulnerability

Aditi Sharma¹, and Dr. Swapnil Nema²

¹Global Nature Care Sangathan's Group of Institutions, Jabalpur, MP, India

²Global Nature Care Sangathan's Group of Institutions, Jabalpur, MP, India

Abstract— The existing techniques and strategies are not sufficient enough to handle most of the vulnerabilities due to its complex nature, and the lack of sophistication in the current input validation techniques. Cross site scripting attack is considered a very dangerous attack for web security. The proposed work identifies the websites with XSS vulnerabilities. Many existing methods are used to detect vulnerabilities, but the proposed work detects as well as rejects the XSS website. It describes the procedure to map the injected probability, to detect the presence of an injected string. The proposed architecture does not demand any source code modifications, and performs detailed analysis at negligible computational overheads without false positives or false negatives. The proposed approach has a fully automated probability assessment procedure to build a legal probability model and has a validation technique to match the dynamic user with the design template.

Keywords— XSS, Vulnerability, AI, Entropy, www, KDD, CP.

I. INTRODUCTION

Websites like Twitter Facebook, and Google have also been harassed by this attack already [6]. Data extraction and machine learning have been providing different methods for a long time to identify different types of web application vulnerabilities. [4]. For a given period of time, feature extraction and classification are used to determine the amount of vulnerability a software has or does not have at all [8].

Figure 1: Data Extraction Process

For the purpose of detection attacker injects malicious code into a legitimate web application [10]. Data extraction can be utilized to separate information from an exceptionally huge informational collection, and we can say that sifting the information comes in crafted by characterization [1]. We do this with the goal that we can consider the information and sort the information.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

There are some limitations of the JavaScript parser, which requires pre-processing before JavaScript to perform certain tasks, such as removing comment tags, and keywords [5]. In addition, most vulnerable components are imported thanks to improper handling of function calls and therefore user input. Rarely these methods are fully capable of their purpose in their work.

III. PROPOSED WORK

A. Transition or Conditional Probability

$$P(A) = \sum_{j=1}^M P(a_j) \quad (1)$$

$$P(A) = 1$$

Because sum of the Probabilities of all the inputs outcomes is 100% or 1.

Similarly,

$$P(B) = \sum_{j=1}^N P(b_k) \quad (2)$$

Transition or conditional Probability (or CP) $P(B/A)$ is nothing but an extension of a probability over which Input A is capable to generate output B.

$$\frac{P(B)}{P(A)} = P(B/A) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Or } P(B) = P(B/A) \cdot P(A) \quad (4)$$

Let, the Probability of generating the desired web site output b1 from the URL a1 is $q=0.8$. The Probability of generating the undesired web site output b2 from the URL a1 is $p=0.2$. a1 is the desired web site URL which has been entered by a client. a2 is the undesired web site URL while a3 is another Mirror web site URL. Usually by entering URL a1, b1 must be accessed, by entering URL a2, b2 must be accessed while by entering URL a3, b3 must be accessed.

The Probability of generating the second Mirror web site output b3 from the URL a3 is denoted by q and the Probability of intentionally provided the wrong web site b2 due to Vulnerability is p . Let, the Probability of generating the second Mirror web site output b3 from the URL a3 is $q=0.7$. The Probability of generating the web site with vulnerability output b2 from the URL a3 is $p=0.3$. a3 is the desired web site URL which has been entered by a client. The URLs probabilities of providing the input are given as follows:

$$P(a1) = 0.3 \quad P(a2) = 0.4 \quad P(a3) = 0.3$$

IV. MODEL FORMULATION

Now we will create an algorithm to prepare the proposed model, which is to be followed to achieve our desired object.

- First define 3 websites URL a1, a2 & a3 and 3 outputs on the screen b1, b2 & b3.
- b1 & b3 are Mirror websites while b2 is not entered by the user.
- Estimate all Input Probabilities P (A) which must be equal to unity.
- Assume Output Probabilities P (B)
- Calculate Conditional Probability P (B/A) in terms of input Probabilities P (A).
- Determine P (A, B)
- Determine CP P (A/B) in terms of input Probabilities P(Y).
- Calculate the Summation of all the Rows individually and denoted by: $P [(a1, a2, a3) / b1]$, $P [(a1, a2, a3) / b2]$ and $P [(a1, a2, a3) / b3]$ respectively.
- Find out the Minimum Value among them. This is the Website with Vulnerability.
- Repeat these steps over and over.
- Block the URL of output of respective Minimum Value. Opera, Mozilla Firefox, and Internet Explorer are used for implementation to support BEEP [3].

B. Joint Probability in terms of A

Relation between Input Probability P (A) and Transition Probability P (B/A) is called Joint Probability P (A, B).

$$P(A, B) = P(A)_d \cdot P(B/A) \quad (5)$$

Where, $P(A)_d$ = diagonal matrix of Input for Noiseless channel only.

C. Joint Probability in terms of B

Relation between Output Probability P (B) and CP P (A/B) is called Joint Probability P (A, B).

$$P(A, B) = P(B) \cdot P(A/B) \quad (6)$$

Let, there are three web sites URL (Uniform Resource Locator) a1, a2 and a3. Through a single click there may be three outputs on the screen b1, b2 and b3. If b1 and b3 are the two Mirror web sites with two separate links of different URLs. It means b1 and b3 have different Databases but both have the same information. If a client would like to access b1 then the Probability of accessing b1 is denoted by q and the Probability of intentionally provided the web site with Vulnerability b2 is p .

Figure 2: Proposed Model

Figure 3: Flow Chart of Proposed Work

A. Illustration of model's implementation process

Transition or Conditional Probability:

$$P(B/A) = \begin{bmatrix} 0.8 & 0.2 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.3 & 0.7 \end{bmatrix}$$

% Calculations

`fprintf ('Server of the Authenticated web site usually observe the Accessing Probabilities of all URLs \n');`

`q1= input ('Enter prob. of desired web site b1 by URL a1')`

`p1= input ('Enter prob. of desired web site b2 by URL a1')`

`q2= input ('Enter prob. of desired web site b2 by URL a2')`

`p3= input ('Enter prob. of desired web site b3 by URL a3')`

`q3= input ('Enter prob. of desired web site b2 by URL a3')`

% Calculation of Transition Probability

`Pa1= input ('Enter the probabilities of entering the URLs a1 =')`

`Pa2= input ('Enter the probabilities of entering the URLs a2 =')`

`Pa3= input ('Enter the probabilities of entering the URLs a3 =')`

Whenever there is a flood of payloads, the method of detecting transitional XSS is more likely to fail [8, 11]. In this work, the method of XSS [2, 4] recognizing attacks is based on the principle of probability. Now, we have to first monitor all the accessibility probabilities by the server in a systematic way to identify the a [9]. After completing the simulation, Google search engine will open in which we have to search for our desired object; In this case our desired object is the audio and video driver.

From equation (5):

$$P(A, B) = P(A)_d \cdot P(B/A)$$

where,

$$P(A)_d = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$P(A, B) = \begin{bmatrix} 0.3 & 0 & 0 & 0.8 & 0.2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.4 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.3 & 0 & 0.3 & 0.7 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0.8(0.3) + 0 & 0.2(0.3) + 0 & 0(0.3) + 0 \\ 0(0.4) + 0 & 1(0.4) + 0 & 0(0.4) + 0 \\ 0(0.3) + 0 & 0.7(0.3) + 0 & 0.3(0.3) + 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

<u>P (b1)</u>	<u>P (b2)</u>	<u>P (b3)</u>
0.24	0.06	0
0	0.4	0
0	0.21	0.09

$$P(B) = [0.24 \quad 0.67 \quad 0.09] \tag{7}$$

0.24	0	0
0	0.67	0
0	0	0.09

From equation (6):

$$P(A, B) = P(B) \cdot P(A/B)$$

$$P(A/B) = \frac{\begin{matrix} 0.24 & 0.06 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.21 & 0.09 \end{matrix}}{\begin{matrix} 0.24 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.67 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.09 \end{matrix}}$$

$$\begin{matrix} 0.24/0.24 & 0.06/0.67 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.4/0.67 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.21/0.67 & 0.09/0.09 \end{matrix}$$

$$P(A/B) = \begin{matrix} 1 & 0.0896 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.5970 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.3134 & 1 \end{matrix}$$

$$P[a_1, a_2, a_3] / b_1 = 1 + 0.0896 + 0 = 1.0896$$

$$P[a_1, a_2, a_3] / b_2 = 0 + 0.5970 + 0 = 0.5970$$

$$P[a_1, a_2, a_3] / b_3 = 0 + 0.3134 + 1 = 1.3134$$

Where,

$$P[(a_1, a_2, a_3) / b_1] = 1.0896$$

$$P[(a_1, a_2, a_3) / b_2] = 0.5970$$

$$P[(a_1, a_2, a_3) / b_3] = 1.3134$$

Minimum Value $P[(a_1, a_2, a_3) / b_2] = 0.5970$

Now, it is clear that the Probability of providing the undesired web site b2 from all the URLs a1, a2, and a3 is very high. However, if we calculate the Output Transition or Conditional Probability P (A/B) then it has been observed that P [a1, a2, a3] / b2] is the lowest value always. Similarly, for n number of web sites the lowest value indicates always the web site with Vulnerability. It may be harmful from the point of view of security or privacy. It must be blocked. Three types of URLs have been introduced in this experiment; out of which the target has been set to completely block the website with lowest CP. While, out of

the remaining two probabilities, the probability, whose value is in the middle remains desired. Always, lowest conditional probability will be the one whose, probability of being vulnerable is q2 i.e., 1 (100%). Now, the conditional probability for this website is to choose between p1 and p3. Whichever of these probability values is less, its conditional probability will also be useful.

Table 1: Precision Calculation

q1	p1	q2	q3	p3	Min (Block)	Middle (Ideal)	Max (XSS)	Middle/Max in %
0.8	0.2	1	0.7	0.3	0.7273	1.1091	1.163	95.3%
0.7	0.3	1	0.8	0.2	0.7273	1.1091	1.163	95.3%
0.9	0.1	1	0.8	0.2	0.8163	1.0612	1.122	94.5%
0.8	0.2	1	0.5	0.5	0.7273	1.1091	1.163	95.3%
0.6	0.4	1	0.7	0.3	0.6557	1.1475	1.196	95.8%
0.8	0.2	1	0.8	0.2	0.7692	1.1154	1.115	100.0%
0.9	0.1	1	0.7	0.3	0.7692	1.0577	1.173	90.1%
0.8	0.2	1	0.8	0.2	0.7692	1.1154	1.115	100.0%
0.9	0.1	1	0.9	0.1	0.8696	1.0652	1.065	100.0%
0.5	0.5	1	0.7	0.3	0.625	1.1406	1.234	92.4%
Gross Ratio								9.58
Precision Rate								96%

From all this work it can be concluded that, the moderate value of conditional probability that is obtained represents a most ideal website. To get this ideal value, we will now calculate the ratio, which is given by:

$$\text{Vulnerability Detection Rate} = \frac{1.0896 + 1.3134}{1.0896 + 1.3134 + 0.5970} * 100\%$$

$$\text{Vulnerability Detection Rate} = \frac{2.403}{3} * 100\%$$

$$\text{Vulnerability Detection Rate} = 80.1\%$$

Pangr gives more complicated solutions and a long or time-consuming algorithm [7]. Gulit Habibi et al. [12] has stated that, the simulation results show that the SVM and n-gram method achieves the highest accuracy with 98%. This research can improve the ability and effective detection of XSS attacks. From the simulation results, the SVM method

that has been added by the n-gram method has the best detection ability.

Upasana Sarmah et al. [10] focuses on studying comprehensively, the detection methods available in the literature for XSS attacks. The proposed method as well as in this method, there is a similarity that the detection methods are classified according to their deployment sites and further sub-classified according to the analysis mechanism they employed. According to the client-server approaches, Upasana Sarmah et al. stated that the Static Analysis method may be used for the Reflected and Stored XSS Vulnerability Detection only; whereas the Dynamic Analysis method may be used for the Attack Detection and Prevention that requires to maintain a cache.

Figure 4: GUI representing all the Conditional Probabilities

From this research result, future work is to implement this capability as an extension in a browser.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We do not have any real data set available, so we are imagining some data instead of real data set which is usually received from the server [9]. The conditional probability which is attained the least, on verifying it is known that this is the most Vulnerability website.

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